

Calibration of the JAGB method for the Magellanic Clouds and Milky Way from Gaia DR3, considering the role of oxygen-rich AGB stars

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ABSTRACT

Appendix F

1. Introduction

The editorial office of A&A made us put Appendix F in Zenodo.

References

- Madore, B. F., Freedman, W. L., Lee, A. J., & Owens, K. 2022, *ApJ*, 938, 125
Marigo, P., Bossini, D., Trabucchi, M., et al. 2022, *ApJS*, 258, 43

Appendix F: Additional figures and tables

Fig. F.1: Absolute J magnitude plotted against $(J - K)_0$ colour and OC turn-off mass, following Fig. 1 in Madore et al. (2022). Stars classified as "TP-AGB" in Marigo et al. (2022) are plotted as C (open circles), M, S, or MS (open triangles), and stars of unknown spectral type (open squares), while stars classified as "E-AGB" are plotted as crosses. Red filled-in symbols indicate stars selected for the calculation of the absolute magnitude, following Madore et al. (2022). Lines indicate colours of 1.2 and 2.0 mag and masses of 1.16 and 3.3 M_{\odot} , see Madore et al. (2022).

Fig. F.2: Cumulative number of stars in the selection box for Model 103 (cf. Fig. 5). Models are for $\rho_0 = 25/\text{kpc}^3$, $H = 200$ pc (red), $\rho_0 = 10/\text{kpc}^3$, $H = 500$ pc (dark blue), and $\rho_0 = 6/\text{kpc}^3$, $H = 1000$ pc (light blue). The number of stars within 1.4 kpc is not subtracted.

Table F.1: Criteria to distinguish the different regions in the *Gaia*-2M diagrams, rescaled to absolute magnitude of the LMC (DML= 18.477).

Group	Criterion
O rich	$W_{RP} - W_K \leq 0.7 + 0.15 \cdot (K_s - 10.8 + \text{DML})^2$
C rich	$W_{RP} - W_K > 0.7 + 0.15 \cdot (K_s - 10.8 + \text{DML})^2$
Faint AGB and RGB	O rich $K_s \geq 11.98 - \text{DML}$ $K_s \geq 13.50 - 5.067 \cdot (W_{RP} - W_K - 0.1) - \text{DML}$
Low-mass AGB	O rich $K_s \geq 10.50 + (W_{RP} - W_K) - \text{DML}$ $[K_s < 11.98 - \text{DML} \text{ or } K_s < 13.50 - 5.067 \cdot (W_{RP} - W_K - 0.1) - \text{DML}]$
Intermediate-mass AGB	O rich $K_s \geq 8.74 + 2 \cdot (W_{RP} - W_K) - \text{DML}$ $K_s \leq 10.50 + (W_{RP} - W_K) - \text{DML}$
Massive AGB and RSG	O rich $K_s \leq 8.74 + 2 \cdot (W_{RP} - W_K) - \text{DML}$
Non-extreme C star	C rich $W_{RP} - W_K \leq 1.7$
Extreme C star	C rich $W_{RP} - W_K > 1.7$

 Fig. F.3: CMDs, *Gaia*-2M diagrams and fits to the LF for models 25 (LMC), 26 (SMC), and 115 (MW)